

ENGLISH FOR SPECIFIC PURPOSES CLASSES THROUGH EFFECTIVE VOCABULARY TEACHING STRATEGIES

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ABSTRACT Today, it has become mandatory for the academicians to rethink their teaching strategies with the changing times. Since there has been a constant change in the teaching methods and techniques all over the world in every subject, vocabulary teaching methods and techniques need desirable and radical changes in a view of the demanding job market in the globalized world.

KEYWORDS: Effective Vocabulary, Teaching Strategies, Prominent Role Of Vocabulary Knowledge, Vocabulary Communication, Activities To Teach New Words.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, our independent Uzbekistan is focusing on developing in every area. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev Miromonovich said: "At the time internalizing new technologies we need to pay attention on the youths' reading books, being friends with books, raising level of reading of population. For all of this, we need to set and promote our national literature and world literature on social network". This speech sounded like an appeal. In addition, we need to notice that glorifying Uzbek literature to the world is the current issue for us. It goes without saying that it is problematic for a specialist to communicate in a foreign language unless one masters enough vocabulary in the field of one's specialty. Aside from this, it is of great importance to be accepted in one's professional sphere and –to communicate a set of professional skills and to perform particular job-related functions. –No matter how well the student learns grammar, no matter how successfully the sounds L2 are mastered, without words to express a wide range of meanings, communication in an L2 just cannot happen in any meaningful way. Effective vocabulary teaching helps develop future specialists' communicative competence. –Vocabulary plays a crucial role in language fluency development and language building||. "Vocabulary is a core component of language proficiency and provides much of the basis for how well learners speak, listen, read, and write". Thus, –effective ESP vocabulary teaching plays a crucial role in successfully implementing ESP programs.

Vocabulary of a language is just like bricks for constructing a building. Like bricks, they are vital for the building of a language. Language is made up of words. If we want to use language effectively, we must have good stock of

vocabulary. We cannot use the language, if we don't know the words of that language. English language has vast vocabulary. It is the richest language of the world. One cannot learn a language without learning vocabulary. Therefore, the study of vocabulary has occupied the central place in teaching learning activities. –If you spend most of your time studying grammar, your English will not improve very much. You will see most improvement, if you learn more words and expressions. You can say very little with grammar, but you can say almost anything with words. This speaks volumes about the significance of vocabulary in learning, developing and enriching English. Even, Wilkins rightly says, –Without grammar very little can be conveyed...but without vocabulary nothing can be conveyed. Vocabulary is a very important means to express our thoughts and feeling, either in spoken or written form. Indeed, neither literature nor language exists without vocabulary. John Drink Water rightly says that words are the bricks the bricks with which the poetry and the literature of the world have been built. It is mainly through using words that we compose and express our thoughts to others. We can tackle our own task through words. It shows words are powerful tools. Famous imperialist poet, Rudyard Kipling says that words are the most powerful drug used by mankind. Those who are rich in vocabulary can speak and write English correctly. Therefore, the study of vocabulary is at the center while learning a new language. English being a second language or foreign language, one needs to learn vocabulary in the systematic way. In fact, without vocabulary communication in a second or foreign language is not possible in a meaningful way. McCarthy (1990) argues: 'No matter how well the student learns grammar, no matter how successfully the sounds of L2 are mastered, without words to express a wide range of meanings, communication in an L2 just cannot happen in any meaningful way'. Vocabulary is needed for expressing meaning and in using the receptive (listening and reading) and the productive (speaking and writing) skills. This obliges ESP teachers at the university to develop students' autonomous learning abilities, to teach them vocabulary learning strategies, and to deliver their vocabulary lessons more creatively. Sharing teaching experiences with colleagues would be particularly helpful in this case. This paper contributes to a deeper understanding of the necessity of ESP vocabulary teaching and learning by ESP teachers. Developing special pedagogical techniques which can help students gain needed skills in mastering ESP vocabulary should be given a great deal of attention.

The prominent role of vocabulary knowledge in second or foreign language learning has been recently recognized by the theorist and researcher in the field. Accordingly, numerous types of approaches, techniques, exercises and practice to teach vocabulary. Nation properly states that teaching vocabulary should not only consist of teaching specific words but also aims at equipping learners with strategies necessary to expand their vocabulary knowledge. By showing actual objects and showing models It is a very useful technique to teach vocabulary to the beginners. The names of many things can be taught by showing actual objects. It gives real experience and sense to the learners. The words like pen, chalk, table, chair, football, flowers, tomato etc. can be taught in the classroom. Real 380 objects or models of real objects are very effective and meaningful in showing meanings but in handling of real objects, a teacher must be practical and should not be superfluous. It is neither possible nor necessary to bring all the things in the classroom. Therefore, some words are to be taught by showing models. They are easily available in the market. They are inexpensive too. Hence, teacher should make frequent use of such models to teach vocabulary. For example, the words like tiger, brain, elephant, aero planet etc. can be shown to the learner. Using demonstrations and showing pictures Teacher can perform some words. It can be fun and frolic. It makes the class student-centered. The teaching of language acquired an applied character, while earlier it was comparatively abstract and theorized. Aristotle also brought out the famous triad of teaching ethics, which is the best match with modern requirements: logo — quality of presentation, pathos — contact with the audience, ethos — attitude towards others. This article will discuss some of the methods. Teacher can act and learners try to imitate it. For example, the words like jump, smile, cry, nap, sleep, and dance can be demonstrated. Miming works well with younger students. You can mime out emotions and everyday activities to teach new words. This method can be practiced at ease. It can win the favors of the students as learners like dramatizations and can easily learn through them. Students at all grade levels need to engage in discussions about their individual pieces of writing. Having opportunities to talk with peers about a topic or idea prior to attempting to write a first draft enables students to refine their thoughts about the writing piece. Thus, when discussion precedes the writing event, the quality of the written product improves. This is true because the writer has probably analyzed, elaborated, questioned, and to some extent justified thoughts and ideas prior to putting them down on paper. Many situations can be

dramatized or demonstrated. This works well with young students or students studying a foreign language to help introduce them to new concepts.

CONCLUSION

Due to the lack of a natural English-speaking environment, students are not always able to use their ESP knowledge in practice, as English is spoken mainly in class. When students face a real need in ESP at work place or job-related situations, they have challenges in speaking and understanding, ESP vocabulary teaching and learning is at the core of an effective ESP learning program. The results of the study have shown that many students of the university aren't in the know of existing vocabulary learning strategies, though if they understood the importance of these strategies they would be able to find relevant information online

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